

AGAINST RELIGIOUS BELIEFS IN STUDENTS STRENGTHENING OF IDEICAL IMMUNITY

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Abstract. *Ideological thinking of students in socially useful labor activities can develop. One of the effective ways to increase students' ideological immunity is "Young ideologues" club. A critical attitude towards foreign ideologies various pedagogy by experienced professors and teachers for development methods are used.*

Keywords: *young ideologues, ideology, immunity, criticism, work.*

Introduction

Strengthening ideological immunity in young students, making them global, cultural and plays an important role in making it stable in relation to ideological features. Students ideological thinking can be developed in socially useful labor activities. For this reason, socially useful work, regardless of intelligent, organizational or physical work, of course, to society must be necessary.

One of the effective ways to increase students' ideological immunity is "Young ideologues" club. In this club, objective assessment of political events, lack of ideas and It aims to teach people how to deal with aloofness from politics. To foreign ideologies experienced professors and teachers to develop a critical attitude different pedagogical methods are used by For example, in the "skip forward" method The leaders of the club discuss current issues of the country and abroad discuss their events. This method allows students to freely express their thoughts and their own helps to form views, especially immunity against religious beliefs is of great importance in strengthening.

The activities of the "Yosh Mafkurachilar" club must be free, as otherwise, students may superficially understand ideological concepts. When setting the goals of the club, it is important to choose socially significant and relevant tasks that should align with the knowledge and experiences of the students. Ideological education for students should be directed towards developing a sense of responsibility towards the people, the homeland, the nation, their family, and their higher educational institution. For example, meetings on the topic "The deeds of our ancestors will always remain in our hearts" can be organized with the participation of students and their parents. During the meeting, students learn about national history and family values by creating their family tree. Connecting family history to national history helps students better understand the history of both the family and the country, and assists them in realizing the importance of national freedom.

Repetition plays a significant role in enhancing the clarity, emphasis and flow of conjunctive structures in English. Below are the key types of repetition employed with conjunctions to improve the expression of ideas:

Students develop their sense of filial duty and positive work assessment through family historical monuments, speeches at parent meetings, and excursions to enterprises. This fosters a sense of national duty and personal responsibility. Improving socially useful labor and ideological-educational processes prepares students for active social engagement in the interests of society. The harmony between ideological and labor education helps students

develop constructive traits. In the modern era, combating religious-extremist movements, such as organizations like "Hizb ut-Tahrir," is of significant importance for students. In this process, it is necessary to rapidly and deeply explain political situations relevant to the time in order to strengthen students' immunity against foreign ideologies. This helps them respond effectively to the threats of various ideologies and enhances their political awareness.

It is important to carry out active propaganda and ideological defense work at every higher educational institution. Necessary materials for both propaganda and counter-propaganda should be prepared and continuously updated. Experienced teachers and leading course students should actively participate in this process as part of propaganda teams. Through the curricula of humanitarian and natural sciences, students must gain a broad and reliable understanding of Uzbekistan's socio-economic situation, national policies, and the advantages of democracy.

It is important to teach students to have a negative attitude towards certain ideas and actions in the process of developing their ideological immunity. In this process, organizations of the "Youth Affairs Agency" should take the lead. Prevention should be the main focus, and measures should be taken by the leadership to prevent the influence of foreign ideologies.

Teachers face a number of problems, including:

- Explain the essence of ideological immunity to students;
- Encourage the use of various scientific manuals to gather information on this topic;
- Study the issues of counter-propaganda and develop skills for clear speech;
- Teach methods of ideological debate and struggle.

The development of historical and scientific concepts plays a crucial role in pedagogical research, particularly in the methodology of teaching social sciences. According to experts, international historical concepts are considered among the most difficult terms to master. If these concepts are not introduced to students in Uzbek in a timely and accurate manner, they may fail to fully understand the true meaning of the historical terms, leading to superficial learning. This can result in memory fatigue and these concepts may be quickly forgotten. Therefore, presenting historical and scientific concepts in a clear and understandable way is essential to enhance the effectiveness of students' learning.

Studying works of art undoubtedly plays a crucial role in shaping ideological thoughts. Art, especially theater, supports the purification of the spirit and the fostering of spiritual growth. In the late 19th and early 20th centuries, intellectuals chose to express their ideas through education and theater. According to art scholar U. Saidov, theater has a unique significance in this process, and works of art play an important role in purifying the heart. Therefore, it is essential to deeply study works of art, promote ideological thoughts through them, and achieve educational goals.

Theses play a significant role in making presentations more reliable and visual. They should primarily be provided with short and clear questions to attract the audience's attention. This approach helps increase the effectiveness of the presentation.

In today's world, strengthening students' ideological immunity plays a crucial role in stabilizing society and preparing future leaders, specialists, and socially active citizens. It is essential for students to gain not only academic knowledge but also a solid ideological foundation to understand their duties to society and the state. Therefore, various pedagogical approaches and methods should be used to foster this ideological immunity.

1. The Importance of Education in Shaping Ideological Immunity

The foundation of ideological immunity lies in education. Students need to acquire not only academic knowledge but also the ability to analyze social processes, political situations, and economic circumstances. This broadens their worldview and equips them to withstand various ideological influences.

In the educational process, it is crucial to introduce students to national values, historical heritage, and the cultural and moral foundations of their people. This helps students understand and value concepts such as patriotism, devotion, and the defense of the national interest, which are vital for their ideological immunity.

2. The Role of the "Young Ideologists" Club and Expanding its Influence

The "Young Ideologists" club is an effective platform for strengthening students' ideological immunity. In this club, students can express their opinions freely, analyze current political events, and discuss critical issues. Teaching students to critically assess political events and engage in ideological debates strengthens their immunity against foreign ideologies and fosters independent thinking.

The club's activities must allow students to critically analyze social and political issues, offer constructive criticism, and engage in ideological struggle. This environment encourages students to explore different viewpoints and form their own opinions, which is essential for developing their ability to withstand foreign ideological influences.

3. Understanding Historical and Cultural Heritage

Fostering ideological immunity in students also requires deepening their understanding of their nation's historical and cultural heritage. Students who have a strong understanding of their national history are better equipped to withstand foreign ideologies and understand their role in the world. Engaging students in activities like exploring their family history or creating family trees helps them connect personal identity with national heritage and understand the importance of national freedom.

Teaching students the significance of independence and their nation's historical journey enables them to appreciate the value of freedom and take responsibility for preserving their nation's sovereignty.

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